

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF GST IN INTERNATIONAL SCENARIO

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Abstract:

The fiscal policy of India took a key step on 1st July, 2017 as the government implemented Goods and Service Tax (GST). GST is destination-based tax structure which subsumes various indirect taxes at both Centre and State level into a single tax with five slabs with option of availing input tax credit at each state. The reform indicates distinction of tax structure among 160 developed and developing countries around the world. India adopted a dual GST structure based on a pragmatic federal relationship that requires both the Centre and States to play a crucial role in deciding GST structure and rates thereof.

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Introduction

Goods and Service Tax is levied on the sale of goods and services across the country. GST is applicable for both the customer and the manufacturer. It is a destination-based tax. It means GST is to be collected at the point of consumption. It means if product is manufactured in Bhopal and sold in Mumbai, the tax will be levied in Mumbai. Moreover, at every stage of manufacturing process where value is added to the product, GST is collected.

There are mainly three types of GST:

- a) CGST (Central Goods and Service Tax). This GST is collected by the central government on the intrastate transactions.
- b) SGST/UTGST (State Goods & Service Tax/Union Territory Goods & Service Tax). The State Governments/Union Territories collect this tax based on the intra-state supply of goods and services.

- c) IGST (Integrated Goods & Service Tax). This GST is charged on the supply of goods and services between the states/union territories. IGST is shared between the central and state governments.

GST is characterized as follows:

- a) India's GST regime is a perfect example of cooperative federalism between Centre and States.
- b) The process of rationalization of GST rates can be continued.
- c) Value-based classification, specialization-based classification and status of buyers may be removed due to simple tax structure.
- d) The government attempts to provide resolution for industry specific issues and achieved an equilibrium between the industry's expectations and the interest of government and society.
- e) Extensive cooperation and support in facilitating GST compliances by easing timelines for various GST related compliances such as filing of GSTR1 and Annual Returns.
- f) Allocation of GST revenue to states based on consumption-based destination tax on goods and services which had led to equitable growth in Indian states.
- g) The GST system runs under a canopy of strong technological support which had led to technologically driven compliance mechanism thereby reducing personal interface.

Based on the 'One Nation, One Tax' ideology, GST has helped in reducing cascading effect of tax considerably. The concept of e-invoicing ensured a greater transparency in supplier-recipient transactions. The introduction of e-way bill regulated fake invoicing and resulted in increasing substantial portion of GST revenues. India ranks 63rd position among 190 nations of the Doing Business Index published by World Bank in October, 2019.

Worldwide GST structure:

- 1) France was the first country to introduce the GST to reduce tax evasion. More than 140 countries have already implemented GST models. Indian GST model is closely similar to the Canadian model of dual GST. The concept of GST is more or less same like in other countries. However, rates and compliance procedures may differ from country to country depending on requirements of that country. A major difference can be noted that India has multiple rates of GST while in many countries the rate is uniform irrespective of the product. The reason behind this is agriculture is not

recognized as industry and to make averaging of GST rates from 0 to 28 %.

- 2) New Zealand introduced the GST in 1986. Initially the rate of GST was 10%, which later rose to 12.5% in 1989 and finally 15% in 2010. The threshold limit of GST registration is \$ 60000. The registered person can opt to file returns monthly, two-monthly or six-monthly, depending upon the turnover. Suppliers of residential accommodation, NPO's distributing the goods as donation, financial services and renting a residential dwelling etc. are exempted from paying GST.
- 3) Canada has Federal Goods and Service Tax (GST) and Harmonized Sales Tax. The former has just one rate of 5% and latter varies from 0% to 15%. Returns are required to be filed on monthly, quarterly, on annual basis depending on turnover. The threshold exemption limit is 30000 Canadian Dollars.
- 4) Australia implemented GST concept in 2000 at a rate of 10%. In Australia GST is collected by federal government and redistributed to the six states and two territories according to the amount recommended by Commonwealth Grants Commission (CGC) on the basis of the principle of Horizontal Fiscal Equalization (HFE).
- 5) In Malaysia, GST was introduced in the year 2015 at a rate of 6%. It brought down the cost of doing the business in the country, as they shifted the tax burden from manufacturers to consumers.
- 6) Brazil, Argentina and Russia- These countries have independent VATs at the Centre and the States. The 2015 CEA Report states that 'Differences in base and rates weaken administration and compliance and it becomes difficult to manage inter-state transactions.'

World Bank's Observations:

World Bank has pointed out that India's GST system is globally speaking, the toughest with not just the highest tax slabs but also the country with the greatest number of tax slabs. India is among five countries (Italy, Luxemburg, Pakistan and Ghana) that have 4 tax slabs as against 49 countries that have just one another 28 countries that have two slabs. The World Bank also noted that administrative tax compliance may have gone up and the burden might fall on firms. Multiple taxes are also cause of high compliance cost.

GST Reforms Proposed:

- 1) Measures to strengthen cash flow management for tax payers for allowing offset of CGST liability of one or more states with the CGST balance at national level. This sort of mechanism will facilitate the taxpayers in making optimum utilization of their

cash or credit ledger balance.

- 2) Incentivizing end consumers to create a more compliant eco-system to prevent retailers for avoiding reporting GST on their supplies. This may also open avenues for them to avoid paying Income Tax on their income.
- 3) Facility of transfer of balances in cash/credit ledgers across multiple GSTINs of a single legal entity.
- 4) Simplified one form for annual return and reconciliation instead of two forms GSTR-9 and GSTR-9C.
- 5) Strengthening of AAR mechanism for dispute resolutions.
- 6) Non denial of Input Credit availed by the corporates because of suppliers' default due to non-filing of returns.
- 7) The government needs to establish GST Tribunals to reduce litigation timelines and pressure on courts.
- 8) The state authorities for Advance Ruling should ideally also have an independent jurist member, apart from a representative from the tax department.

Impact of GST on Indirect Tax collection in India

Particulars	F Y 2017-18	F Y 2018-19	F Y 2019-20	F Y 2020-21	F Y 2021-22
Average collection in Crores of Rs.	82,294	98,114	101,844	94,732	122,047
Source-GST Collection data of Ministry of Finance					

It shows that average GST collection has increased from Rs. 82294 crores (average) in 2017-18 to Rs. 122047 crores (average) in 2021-22 (considered April & May of 2021-22). It is a positive impact on growth, but in 2020-21 it shows a decline due to Covid pandemic situation.

Impact of GST on Direct Tax collection in India

Financial Year	Corporate Income Tax	Personal Income Tax	Total Direct (Income) Tax
2017	4.85	3.65	8.50
2018	5.71	4.31	10.02
2019	6.63	4.73	11.36
2020	5.57	4.93	10.50
2021	4.57	4.88	9.45
All figures are in Rupees Lakhs Crores			
Source-Finance Ministry Budget Documents.			

Direct tax collection has increased after GST implementation in India. The increase is noticed in above table since 2017 in both personal income tax and corporate income tax. However, during Covid pandemic period direct tax collection had declined.

Conclusion:

India embarked upon the GST considered to be the most revolutionary and radical tax reform since independent India. Despite initial teething issues the move and overall progress during the last four years. India had witnessed a very progressive, & growth catalyst regime. It greatly helped India in achieving the ambitious government's target of bringing in ease of doing business as one India Market. While the GST regime ushered in numerous benefits, particularly in terms of removing tax cascading impact, compliance simplification, smoothening supply chain, tax consolidation, it has also encountered some challenges for MSME sector, input tax reconciliation for corporates, increase of tax base and formalization of economy.

References:

1. Finance Ministry Budget documents
2. Web site of Ministry of Finance
3. WIRC Bulletins of 2021